

Forecasting Quality Performance in Manufacturing SMEs: A Stochastic Simulation Framework for Process Investments

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Abstract

The manufacturing industry, including its maquila sector, faces constant pressure to meet higher quality standards. As a result, investments in process improvement have become indispensable components of annual planning for companies operating in this industry. Usual priorities cover technology for quality assurance, particularly mechanisms to prevent errors. To make a sound investment decision, it is imperative to conduct a thorough analysis of the current state and the short-term trends in the quality of the plant, which creates an excellent scenario to perform simulation work. Simulation has been used as an effective tool for validation in manufacturing fields [1],[2],[3]. However, it appears Small- and Medium-sized Enterprises (SMEs) in the maquila sector have not yet widely adopted this approach, indicating potential for innovative contributions. To address this challenge, we propose a stochastic simulation model that utilizes historical data patterns to forecast quality performance for upcoming periods. Our model can be applied to the manufacturing operations of SMEs, providing a more robust basis for decision-making, and enabling stakeholders to make more confident investment strategies for quality improvement initiatives.

References

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